

A PROCEDURE FOR STUDYING DELAMINATION IN COMPLEX STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: When designing complex parts made out with laminated composites the problem of delamination is always present. Delamination studies are well known and today it is possible performing quite detailed analysis to obtain a full and accurate three dimensional stress field that lets the designer know about onset of delamination. Nevertheless, one of the most important problems to perform numerical analysis of the three dimensional stress field in composite materials, is the huge amount of computer resources required for these calculations. In most complex structures, this problem will make unfeasible performing these studies, being necessary performing destructive testing on prototypes to check the interlaminar shear strength of the structure.

To solve this problem, there are also some well known techniques as global-local approaches that can be used for designing with good results. From the engineer point of view, the problem that usually they are not implemented in commercial finite element codes so that engineers can not use them for everyday calculations.

KEYWORDS. delamination, finite element calculations, composite materials design, practical engineering design

INTRODUCTION

Composite laminated materials exhibit some particular behaviours that make them unique materials between all the used for engineering applications. From the very beginning of the development of these materials, mathematical theories to design structures were postulated, being one of the more classical ones the Classical Laminated Theory (CLT) [1, 2]. These initial theories were well fitted for most of the structures that were made with composite materials in those times. Nevertheless, with the popularisation of composites, new applications with higher stresses and much higher responsibility have been done up to now that primary structures in aircrafts, sportive cars, motorcycles, sporting equipment etc. are being made with composites [3-4].

Not only the responsibility of the structures has been incremented but also the complexity of the parts. In the beginning, most of the applications for composites were restricted to plates or quite simple parts platewise with very few problems for the nowadays designer. Usually the parts were not loaded to high so that some of the behaviours arising in structures highly loaded were not known.

It was in 1970 when Pipes & Pagano [5] solved a real three dimensional problem by means of finite differences and demonstrated the existence of interlaminar stresses in the vicinity of the free edges where equilibrium is not satisfied only by the stresses σ_x , σ_y , τ_{xy} appearing the so

called interlaminar stresses, namely interlaminar normal stress σ_z and interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} τ_{zy} . These stresses only appear (onset of delamination) when the structure is loaded so that the stress in some of the layers is close to the first ply failure strength for most of the materials and stacking sequences.

From that date, delamination has always been a subject of concern for the engineers dealing with composite design. Methods for solving the calculations are perfectly known as finite element analysis, nevertheless, to solve the three dimensional problem with finite element calculations is such a huge task that makes it unfeasible for most of the engineering problems. It is clear that new approaches for studying delamination should be developed to make these calculations affordable for the commercial finite element codes and computers currently available.

This paper presents two other possibilities, being the first one a technique of mesh transitions with couplings and constraining equations. In the areas where the mesh is not fully three-dimensional, simplifications on the material properties must be performed through the using of Classical Laminated Theory on equivalent groups of plies. These calculations can be performed in one or several shots depending on the knowledge that the designer has of the behaviour of the structure. A full three dimensional mesh with one element per layer in thickness can be made in the areas of interest while coarser meshes can be used in less loaded areas.

CLASSICAL LAMINATED THEORY AND EVOLUTION

The most known theory for calculating laminated composite structures is the CLT [6]. This theory is well established on the basis of both the hypothesis of plane stress in each one of the layers as in the Kirchoff one for thin plates, and it has been demonstrated to work perfectly with plates and platewise structures with a high length to thickness ratio. The basic set of equations for this theory is:

$$u(x,y,z) = u_0(x,y,z) - z \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x}(x,y)$$

$$v(x,y,z) = v_0(x,y,z) - z \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y}(x,y)$$

$$w(x,y,z) = w_0(x,y)$$

Being the coordinate system for the plate defined in the next figure:

Fig.1 Model used in the Classical Laminated Theory

With CLT, in plane stresses σ_x , σ_y , τ_{xy} can be obtained but interlaminar stresses σ_z , τ_{xz} , τ_{zy} are not available as the assumption of keeping transverse cross sections perpendicular to the neutral axis of the plate has been made (Kirchoff hypothesis).

To solve this problem a number of higher order theories have been postulated. Most of them try to use the simplicity of the CLT while introducing more terms depending on the thickness, z , in a nonlinear way (exponents of z) to let the cross section of the laminate suffer deformations so that they do not need to finish perpendicular to the neutral axis in the deformed shape of the plate.

The general form of these higher order theories follow the next set of equations:

$$\begin{aligned}u(x, y, z) &= u_0(x, y, z) - z \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x}(x, y) + u_3 z^3 + \dots + u_n z^n \\v(x, y, z) &= v_0(x, y, z) - z \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y}(x, y) + v_3 z^3 + \dots + v_n z^n \\w(x, y, z) &= w_0(x, y)\end{aligned}$$

The more terms in z^n , the higher accuracy can be obtained in the interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} , τ_{zy} but the more degrees of freedom that are introduced in the set of equations. Many authors have presented their own theories that can be solved with expressions like the following one, presented by Murthy:

$$\begin{aligned}u &= u_0 + \left(\frac{5}{4}z - \frac{5}{3h^2}z^3 \right) \frac{12}{h^3} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} uz dz + \left(\frac{1}{4}z - \frac{5}{3h^2}z^3 \right) \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} \\v &= v_0 + \left(\frac{5}{4}z - \frac{5}{3h^2}z^3 \right) \frac{12}{h^3} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} vz dz + \left(\frac{1}{4}z - \frac{5}{3h^2}z^3 \right) \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} \\w &= w_0\end{aligned}$$

Nevertheless, and although interlaminar stresses can be computed with good accuracy depending on the theory chosen, interlaminar normal stress σ_z is still out of the scope of the calculations. From experimentation and resolution of the true three dimensional state of stresses, it is known that interlaminar normal stress σ_z is responsible of most of the failures caused by interlaminar stresses so that it is very important including its calculation in the method used to design structures.

FINITE ELEMENT CALCULATIONS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

CLT is a very powerful tool for solving parts with a rather simple geometry. If the parts being designed are more complex or a higher precision is required in the analysis, Finite Element Method (FEM) should be used to perform the calculations. There are several steps increasing the complexity of the calculations to approach the real behaviour when designing composite structures with FEM.

Along the presentation of the different approaches for calculating composite structures, examples of results obtained using commercial codes MARC and ANSYS will be shown.

All the calculations are performed on a simple plate made out with T300/5208 carbon-epoxy with an stacking sequence of $[0/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/90]_s$ and a total thickness of 1 mm. The load

introduced is a deformation of 0.72% that will cause onset of delamination in the sample. Dimensions of the plate analysed are 120 mm. length and 30 mm. width [7].

Orthotropic material properties are included in the next table:

Table 1. Material properties used where all the values are expressed in GPa.

E_x	E_y	E_z	G_{xy}	G_{xz}	G_{yz}	μ_{xy}	μ_{xz}	μ_{yz}
181	10.3	10.3	7.17	7.17	4.13	0.28	0.28	0.51

Laminated Shell Approach

This is the simplest way of calculating composite structures by means of FEM. The structure must be modelled following its neutral axis to obtain a shell element model. Most of the software currently available allows the user to introduce offsets to simulate changes in the thickness of the laminate.

Basic theory to solve the problem is, again, the CLT although in most cases, a higher order theory is used so that normals to the centre plane in the undeformed configuration are supposed to remain straight although not necessarily normal to the centre plane in the deformed configuration.

ANSYS calculations are performed in this way so that interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} and τ_{zy} can be calculated. Besides that, an assumption to obtain a parabolic shear strain distribution is made. The basic matrix equations solved by this code are [8]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \{N\} \\ \{M\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [E_0] & [E_1] \\ [E_1] & [E_2] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\epsilon\} \\ \{\phi\} \end{Bmatrix}$$

In this expression, the submatrices $[E_0]$, $[E_1]$, and $[E_2]$ are computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} [E_0] &= \sum_{j=1}^{N_l} \int [T_m]_j^T [D]_j [T_m]_j \, dr \\ [E_1] &= \sum_{j=1}^{N_l} \int r [T_m]_j^T [D]_j [T_m]_j \, dr \\ [E_2] &= \sum_{j=1}^{N_l} \int r^2 [T_m]_j^T [D]_j [T_m]_j \, dr \end{aligned}$$

This equations are nothing else that the CLT but expresses in terms of FEM formulation in which the matrix $[T_m]$ is the layer to element transformation matrix and $[D]$ is the stress-strain law in each layer. All the integrals are performed between the lower dimension of each laminae and its upper dimension. The system of equations is formulated so at a global scale element by element not performing integration through thickness. This leads to a calculation of the interlaminar stresses based on the incremental form of the elasticity equations.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial z} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Taking a look now to another commercial FEM code, MARC, it performs real integration through thickness, locating integration points inside each layer rather than on their interfaces. Number of integration points can be selected by the user [9].

Next figures show comparative results of interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} between the interface of layer 2 and 3 from the calculations performed with ANSYS and MARC.

Fig. 2. Stresses τ_{xz} in the interface between layers 2 and 3 obtained with ANSYS

Fig. 3. Stresses τ_{xz} in the interface between layers 2 and 3 obtained with MARC

Full Three Dimensional Calculations

The opposite way to the laminated shell approach useful for calculating composite parts to know the real stress field, is performing a full three dimensional analysis with brick elements including at least one element in thickness for each layer. This procedure leads to very accurate results, nevertheless its computational cost is enormous. It should be beard in mind that interlaminar stresses usually appear in a dimension from the free edge that is similar to the thickness of the laminate. This means that the number of elements to be introduced in the vicinity of the free edges is very large. As FEM requires connectivity between nodes to ensure displacement continuity, the total mesh will have many thousands of elements even for very simple plates.

The next figures show the result of the calculations performed using ANSYS, where interlaminar normal stresses σ_z and interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} can be seen at different interfaces between layers of the material. These stresses have been evaluated at the integration points and they have been directly extrapolated to the nodes without performing any averaging [10].

Fig. 4. Interlaminar normal stress in the symmetry plane

Fig. 5. Interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} in the interface 2-3 (+45°-45°)

This figures should be compared with the ones obtained by Pipes and Pagano and many other in Bibliography. This comparison shows that the shape of the stress distribution is the expected one.

Now, the same calculations are repeated but using the commercial FEM code MARC to check results between both of them. Results and FEM meshing can be seen in the next figures.

Figure 6. Detail of the FEM meshing performed with MARC

Fig. 7. Interlaminar normal stress in the symmetry plane

Fig. 8. Interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} in the interface 2-3 (+45°-45°)

Differences between both codes is small, as the calculations performed with ANSYS show maximum values of 112.82 MPa and 44.695 MPa for the interlaminar normal stress and the interlaminar shear stress respectively while in MARC, these stresses are 99 MPa for the interlaminar normal stresses σ_z and 42 MPa for the interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} .

Differences in the interlaminar normal stresses are caused by the different mesh density used in both models, and, more important, the stresses in MARC are in the nodes, so, extrapolation from the integration points has been performed producing the differences that can be seen in the results.

Results from these calculations are very accurate to calculate interlaminar stresses, nevertheless its cost is too high as to perform these analysis on real structures. This is the main reason why another approach should be followed if these kind of calculations must be done.

Three Dimensional Approach with Different Mesh Densities

It is perfectly known that interlaminar stresses are only a concern in several restricted areas of composite materials. Only in the vicinity of free edges, changes in the thickness of the structure, holes and damages or impacts problems caused by these out of plane stresses can be expected.

Performing normal FEM models have the problem that to ensure the mesh required in the areas of interest, and due to connectivity reasons, the mesh density in the entire model will be too high. A possible way to solve this problem is performing mesh transition between the area of interest and the rest of the model but this point will mean that tetrahedral will appear increasing the “numerical stiffness” of the structure and leading to a lack of accuracy in the calculations. Besides that, to have a reasonable mesh with tetrahedral, the number of elements must be much higher than meshing with hexahedra.

MARC commercial FEM code, specially devoted to non linear and contact calculation, has a very interesting possibility using contact [11]. With this possibility, a glued contact between two parts of a structure with different meshes can be performed. This means that a coarse mesh can be made in the area where stresses are not going to be a concern while a much finer

mesh can be made in the area where interlaminar stresses will appear. The basis of this method can be seen in the next figure.

Fig. 9. Sketch of the calculations with mesh transition

In the case the analyst does not know beforehand the behaviour of the structure a first calculation performed with inexpensive laminated shell elements can be performed before starting with the full three dimensional calculations. After knowing the stresses an expansion of the dimension of the elements to obtain a full three dimensional model can be performed.

The area in which the elements are simulating a group of layers must be modelled with their equivalent properties or three dimensional layered brick elements must be used. If the first possibility is used, the group of layers must be symmetrical for being capable of having a subset whose properties are orthotropic. The way to obtain the equivalent layer material properties is through the CLT. Total stiffness matrix [A] or [D] for the group of layers must be formulated depending on the loads introduced to the laminate (the first for plane stress and the second for bending). This matrix is composed of three submatrices in the following form:

Engineering constants to be introduced in the equivalent single layer can be obtained, in the case of plane stress, from the normalized plane stiffness matrix [a*]. Terms in [a*] are calculated as [12]:

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N [\overline{Q}_{ij}] (h_k - h_{k-1})$$

$$[a] = [A]^{-1}; [a^*] = h[a]$$

In this expression, $[\overline{Q}_{ij}]_k$ is the stiffness matrix of each lamina k, referred to the plate axis, h is the total thickness of the laminate and h_k and h_{k-1} are the position of the upper face and the lower one for each layer referred to the center plane of the laminate. From here, engineering constants are obtained as:

$$E_1 = \frac{1}{a_{11}^*}, E_2 = \frac{1}{a_{22}^*}, E_6 = \frac{1}{a_{66}^*}$$

$$\mu_{21} = \frac{-a_{21}}{a_{11}}, \mu_{61} = \frac{-a_{61}}{a_{11}}, \mu_{62} = \frac{-a_{62}}{a_{11}}$$

$$\mu_{12} = \frac{-a_{12}}{a_{22}}, \mu_{16} = \frac{-a_{16}}{a_{66}}, \mu_{26} = \frac{-a_{26}}{a_{66}}$$

For the case of bending, equations are obtained in the same manner but substituting the matrix $[a^*]$ by $[d^*]$ that is computed from:

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^N [\overline{Q}_{ij}] (h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3)$$

$$[d] = [D]^{-1}; [d^*] = \frac{h^3}{12} [d]$$

In the case of the laminate used in the example, there is an only possibility to obtain a single equivalent layer symmetrical, as is taking the full material as a layer. This means that the area far from the point of interest will have an only element in the thickness direction, while the full three dimensional mesh will have eight elements in thickness (one for each layer).

Fig. 10. Interlaminar normal stresses σ_z in the plane of symmetry with mesh transition

Fig. 11. Interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} in the interface 2-3 with mesh transition

A detail of the transition between the area with one element in thickness direction (equivalent single layer) and the full three dimensional mesh with one element for each layer can be seen in the next figure.

Fig. 12 Detail of the mesh transition

It can be seen how with this approach, interlaminar normal stresses σ_z obtained are 107.4 MPa while interlaminar shear stresses τ_{xz} are 40.15 MPa. These values should be compared with the ones obtained in previous three dimensional analysis to check the accuracy of this method.

Next table shows a summary of the results.

Table 2. Comparison of results

Calculation	σ_z (MPa)	τ_{xz} (MPa)
(1) ANSYS 3-D	112.82	44.695
(2) MARC 3-D	87	41.8
Difference (1)-(2)	22.8%	6.46%
(3) MARC contact	107.4	40.15
Difference (1)-(3)	4.8%	10.16%
Difference (2)-(3)	19%	3.95%

Submodelization Techniques

A second choice, or even better in coordination with previous approach of rigid contacts, as submodelization techniques are, can be used to perform simpler analysis using approaches not demanding so much resources, and performing a second detailed three dimensional analysis on the area where stresses are higher or delamination failures are suspected to appear. Besides that, this technique becomes a powerful tool if different codes are to be used in the analysis as it allows for an straightforward portability of the models provided adequate boundary conditions are computed in the cutting areas.

The basic idea of this procedure, proposed in ANSYS manuals [13], can be splitted into four main steps:

1. Performing a FEM analysis on a coarse inexpensive mesh.
2. Cutting and saving to a file the displacement field obtained in the boundaries of the area where a new model is to be made.
3. Meshing the new area with a finer mesh. This step can include transition between shell and solids if necessary.
4. Interpolation of the displacements saved to a file to apply them to the new nodes in the boundary of the remeshed area. After this, rerun the problem

Application of this procedure to the calculation of composite structures can be made as proposed in the next figure.

Fig.13 Sketch of submodelization

From the trials already performed by the author, the best approximation can be a mixture between the submodelization and the mesh transition. This is so because cutting of boundaries must not be performed too close to the area of interest to avoid Saint Venant effects. If cut is made far away of that zone, three dimensional mesh can be again too large to be solved in an economical way. So, if submodelization is made far away from the interesting area, followed by a mesh transition procedure with contacts, total number of degrees of freedom can be reasonable without penalising accuracy.

CONCLUSIONS

Along this paper, different possibilities for calculating the three dimensional stress field in composite structures has been shown. Two of the proposed techniques are very attractive to the designer as accurate results can be obtained without requiring too much computer resources for solving the set of equations.

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